

The Impact of The Social Media Marketing on E-Wom Communication

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Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of social media marketing (SMM) on consumers' electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) behaviors and purchase intentions, specifically identifying which SMM dimensions drive these outcomes. Quantitative analysis method was used in the study. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire from a sample of 620 online consumers active on platforms such as Trendyol, Hepsiburada, and Amazon. Findings indicate that entertainment, trendiness, and personalization significantly influence e-WOM behavior. Notably, interactivity was found to have no significant effect on e-WOM. On the other hand, interaction, trending, and personalization were significant determinants of purchase intention, while entertainment did not have a direct impact. These results suggest that while hedonic content drives peer-to-peer sharing, utilitarian and interactive elements are more critical for driving actual purchase intent

Key words: Social Media Marketing, Electronic Word of Mouth, Purchase Intention

JEL Code: M30, M31, M37

1. Introduction

The rapid global proliferation of social media use has fundamentally transformed business marketing strategies. Social media, which has become part of the daily lives of billions of people worldwide, provides a critical platform for brand communication and customer engagement (Appel, Grewal, Hadi, & Stephen, 2020). Beyond traditional marketing, social media marketing allow businesses to engage in two-way interaction with consumers through online platforms and build brand communities. Marketing activities conducted through networks such as

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Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, in particular, offer the opportunity to reach large audiences at low cost and create engagement through content sharing (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Consequently, social media marketing has become an essential tool for modern business world and has emerged as an important element of the marketing mix.

One of the key concepts in this digital ecosystem is electronic word-of-mouth communication (e-WOM). According to a widely accepted definition in the literature, e-WOM refers to “*any positive or negative sharing by current, potential, or former consumers about a product or company via the internet*” (Hennig-Thurau, Gwinner, Walsh, & Gremler, 2004). Compared to traditional WOM, e-WOM content can spread to very large audiences in a short time on online platforms and remain accessible for a long time (Dellarocas, 2003; Cheung and Thadani, 2012). Consumers are increasingly taking into account user reviews and shared experiences on social media before making a purchase. Indeed, research shows that consumers who receive positive e-WOM messages experience increased brand trust and product purchase intent (Cheung and Thadani, 2012; Atito, Abd El-Jalil, Rady, and Fawy, 2023).

According to Fishben and Aizen, (1975) “purchase intention refers to the subjective probability of an individual performing a purchase” (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). In marketing literature, purchase intention is considered an important predictor and indicator of actual purchasing behavior (Ajzen, 1991, Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The consumer's purchase intention is shaped by personal needs, attitudes, and environmental factors, and interactions and information sharing in the digital environment, in particular, can influence this intention (Lin and Shen, 2023). Content encountered on social media, other consumers' comments, and influencer recommendations can create a sense of trust in consumers, thereby strengthening their purchasing tendency. In this context, it is argued that social media marketing activities and e-WOM have an integrated effect on shaping consumers' purchase intentions.

Social media marketing, e-WOM and purchase intention interaction are particularly important for the scholars. With the proliferation of online shopping, consumers are heavily influenced by social media content and user reviews when making purchasing decisions. Leading e-commerce platforms such as Trendyol, Hepsiburada, and Amazon actively use social media marketing to reach millions of followers and encourage e-WOM interactions among users. On these platforms, consumers share their experiences with products via social media and on-site reviews, thereby influencing other consumers' purchasing decisions. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine the effect of social media marketing activities on consumers' e-WOM tendencies and purchase intentions. Within this conceptual framework the study aims to give contributions to the literature about the reflections of digital marketing strategies on consumer behaviour.

2. Literature Review

Social Media Marketing

Social media refers to online applications, platforms, and environments designed to facilitate interactions, collaborations, and content sharing. Social media comes in various forms and includes many types such as weblogs, social blogs, microblogs, wikis, podcasts, images, videos, ratings, and social bookmarks (Mohammadpour, Arbatani, Gholipour, Farzianpour, & Hosseini, 2014). According to Statista (2024) data, the number of social media users worldwide has reached 5.17 billion (64% of the population). The most widely used social media platforms are Facebook (2.96 billion), YouTube (2.5 billion), WhatsApp (2.3 billion), Instagram (2.2 billion) and TikTok (1.6 billion). From Turkey's perspective, social media usage rates are above the global average. According to data from We Are Social and Meltwater (2024), 80.8% of Turkey's total population are active social media users, which equates to approximately 69 million people. The most widely used social media platforms in Turkey are Instagram, WhatsApp, YouTube and TikTok, in that order. Users in Turkey spend an average of 2 hours and 44 minutes per day on social media, with this time increasing further among younger age groups. These statistics demonstrate that social media has become an effective tool for communication, marketing and information gathering at both global and local levels. The increase in user numbers and interaction times on platforms highlight the potential of social media marketing, and its strategic importance for businesses is growing every year. Social networks began as a tool for people to stay connected with or reconnect with friends and family. Today, however, social media has transformed the internet into not only a source of information but also a source of influence (Hanna, Rohm, and Crittenden, 2011) and businesses can reach the global market through social media thanks to millions of users worldwide (Green et al., 2018). Social media is helping to increase consumer engagement with brands and build stronger, long-term relationships. It also enables marketing strategies to be optimised more quickly by providing the opportunity to receive immediate feedback, as it allows direct access to consumers.

Many studies have addressed social media-related components. Among these studies, Kim and Ko (2012) examined five constructs of perceived SSM activities of luxury fashion brands: entertainment, interaction, trendiness, personalization, and word of mouth marketing. Sano (2014) examined the dimensions of social media marketing as interaction, trendiness, customization and perceived risk. In this study, entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and perceived risk dimensions used by Seo and Park (2018) were used as variables.

Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM)

As studied in Kim and Ko (2012), one of the components of social media is word of mouth can effect business strategies in positive or negative way. Studies show that a customer's sincere recommendation can significantly influence potential customers' purchasing decisions (Elwalda & Lu, 2016). For businesses, negative

WOM poses a threat that can lead to reputational and revenue losses. Word of mouth spreads quickly about a bad experience, especially through social media and online platforms, and it can now reach a much wider audience in a short time. E-WOM is seen as the digitalized version of traditional word-of-mouth communication and is considered the most effective form of communication that affects consumers' purchasing decisions (Iqbal, Khan, Malik, & Faridi, 2022).

The impact of eWOM on consumer behavior has been extensively studied in the marketing literature. A meta-analysis study has shown that online consumer reviews significantly influence many outcomes, from brand attitudes to purchase intentions (Cheung and Thadani, 2012). Another example is a book industry study that found that reader reviews on Amazon.com significantly inflated book sales rankings (Chevalier and Mayzlin, 2006). Similarly, studies conducted for the film industry have found that films that receive many positive reviews on the internet before their release have higher box office performance (Liu, 2006; Duan, Gu, & Whinston, 2008). These findings indicate that eWOM is related to marketing success in terms of both quantity (number of comments) and quality (content of comments). For this reason, the study of Mikalef et al. (2013) was used for e-wom dimension.

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention deals with a consumer's tendency and desire to purchase a specific product in the future. According to Lin and Shen (2023), purchase intention is a consumer's conscious orientation toward a product or brand and is the psychological equivalent of the consumer's likelihood of purchasing a particular product. Consumers' purchase intention is influenced by multidimensional elements such as cultural, social, personal and psychological factors (Qoriyah, Gemina, & Yulianingsih, 2025).

Literature studies on the relationships between the research variables of purchase intention, eWOM and social media marketing are summarized as follows.

Table 1. Literature studies on the relationships between the research variables of purchase intention, E-WOM and social media marketing

Studies	Variables	Findings
Fan and Miao (2012)	Customer expertise, involvement, and rapport to acceptance and use of electronic word of mouth in making purchasing decision	perceived eWOM credibility has a significant effect on eWOM acceptance and intent to purchas
Mikalef et al. (2013)	In the research, the factors affecting product browsing on social media were separated based on utilitarian and hedonic motivation theory.	Results showed that the concepts of “convenience” and “product selection” are important among the utilitarian motivations that affect the intention to browse products on social media, and the concepts of “idea exploration” and “adventure” are important among the hedonic motivations.

Zhao, Wang, Tang ve Zhang (2020)	They investigated the effects of e-WOM on trust and its reflection on purchase intention by taking into account the social-psychological distance of consumers from the perspective of information quality.	According to the findings, it was determined that social psychological distance mediates the relationship between information quality and trust, and trust is positively related to purchase intention.
Pramudhita and Mediawati (2021)	They examined the role of social media marketing activities in increasing e-WOM and visitor intention through brand equity.	social media marketing activities positively and significantly affect brand value, brand value e-WOM and visit intention.
Iqbal et al. (2022)	They examined the comparative effects of e-WOM on online shopping platforms and social networking platforms on the purchase intention of smartphones.	The study helps online companies understand consumer purchasing behavior and highlighted that E-WOM on online shopping platforms is more effective compared to E-WOM on social media platforms.
Winarno and Indrawati (2022)	examined the impact of social media marketing and e-WOM on the purchase intention of a brand's products	social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on e-WOM.
Atito et al. (2023)	They aimed to examine the effect of e-WOM via social media on purchase intention. e-trust was used as a mediating variable.	it was determined that e-WOM has a significant effect on purchase intention and e-trust is a partial mediator of this effect.
Romadhoni, Akhmad, Naldah and Rossanty (2023)	They aimed to determine the impact of social media marketing and e-WOM on purchase decisions and purchase intention.	According to the results, social media marketing and e-WOM positively affect purchasing decisions.
Ardani (2024)	examined the effects of social media and brand image on purchase intention and the mediating effect of e-WOM.	showed that social media and brand image have a positive and significant effect on customers' purchase intention both directly and through e-WOM.
Pang and Wang (2025)	Examine the relationships among customer motivations, active participation, e-WOM and purchase intentions based on Uses and Gratifications Theory and Social Exchange Theory.	functional, hedonic and social motivations positively affect the active participation of WeChat users.

Although social media marketing has become a central tool for online retailers, the literature still offers an incomplete picture of which specific SMM dimensions actually shape consumer outcomes. Many studies examine social media marketing at a general level, but fewer distinguish between its key components, such as entertainment, trendiness, interactivity, and personalization, or test how each dimension differently influences consumers' electronic word-of-mouth and purchase intentions.

For example, Hasan et al.(2023) stated that the role of social media marketing dimensions in brand outcomes had been underexplored: “The significance of value co-creation as the underlying mechanism between social media marketing and brand authenticity has received little scholarly attention. Likewise, the question of whether social media marketing dimensions help build brand authenticity perceptions has not been investigated (Hasan et al. 2023). Cheung et al.(2021) similarly treat SMM as a multi-dimensional construct and report mixed effects: “Entertainment, customization and eWOM are the key predictors” of value co-creation intention, but “the impact of interactivity and trendiness on value co-creation intention is non-significant (Cheung et al. 2021). Simanjuntaka et al.(2022) also find dimension-specific results in smartphones: “Interaction, Word-of-Mouth, Social media marketing, Entertainment and Trendiness have insignificant effects on purchase intentions of Smartphones while Customization has significant effects (Simanjuntaka et al. 2022). Ho et al.(2024) report the opposite pattern in another context, where entertainment, interaction, customization, and word-of-mouth were significant, but trendiness was not (Ho et al. 2024).

These studies leaves a practical and theoretical gap, because managers need to know not only whether SMM matters, but which elements of SMM are most effective for encouraging sharing and stimulating buying behavior. To address this gap, the present study examines the separate effects of SMM dimensions on e-WOM and purchase intention among online consumers using major e-commerce platforms. By identifying which aspects of social media marketing drive peer-to-peer sharing and which lead more directly to purchase decisions, the study provides more specific evidence for both marketing theory and digital marketing strategy. Its findings can help online retailers design more targeted social media campaigns that emphasize the features most likely to generate consumer engagement and conversion.

3. Methodology

Research Model and Hypothesis

This research was established using quantitative methods. Quantitative research methods are research approaches that allow for objective, measurable, and statistical analyses, generally enabling inferences about the population based on a sample (Creswell, 2014).

This study utilizes both primary data collection methods and an online survey method via Google Forms for data collection. data collection was conducted between July 2024 and October 2024. The study's population consists of consumers who shop through Trendyol, Hepsiburada, and Amazon in Turkey. Since the population is very large, convenience sampling was used. For very large populations in social sciences, the sample size is at least 384 for a 95% confidence level (Gürbüz and Şahin, 2018). Based on responses from online surveys, the sample size was determined to be 620. Therefore, at a 95% confidence level, the sample's representativeness of the population is quite high.

The questionnaire prepared for data collection in the study included a personal information form, Social Media Marketing scale (Seo and Park, 2018), Electronic Word-of-Mouth Communication scale (Mikalef et al., 2013), and Purchase Intention scale (Zengin and Arıç1, 2017). The SPSS 25.0 programme was used to analyse data. Frequency and percentage distributions were used to describe participants' demographic characteristics in the initial analysis. Regression analysis was then applied to test the hypotheses. On the other hand, this research is correlational in nature, in line with the aim of the study. Figure 1 shows the research model, which is based on previous studies.

Figure 1. Research model

The hypotheses of the study are listed as follows:

H₁: Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.

- H_{1a}: The entertainment dimension has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.
- H_{1b}: The interactivity dimension has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.
- H_{1c}: The trendiness dimension has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.
- H_{1d}: The personalization dimension has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.
- H_{1e}: The perceived risk dimension has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.

H₂: Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

- H_{2a}: The entertainment dimension has a significant effect on purchase intention.
- H_{2b}: The interactivity dimension has a significant effect on purchase intention.
- H_{2c}: The trendiness dimension has a significant effect on purchase intention.
- H_{2d}: Personalization has a significant effect on purchase intention.
- H_{2e}: Perceived risk has a significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication.

H₃: Electronic word-of-mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

Findings

According to demographic characteristics of sample, the 26-35 age group accounted for the largest share of the sample at 43.2%, followed by participants aged 18-25 at 31.1%. Therefore, the sample consists predominantly of young and young adult participants. The female ratio is 44.5%, while the male ratio is 55.5%. This indicates that the genders are relatively evenly distributed, but males are in the majority. More than half of the participants (53.9%) are university graduates. Therefore, it can be seen that the vast majority of the sample has a university-level education. The majority of participants (36.8%) reported monthly incomes between 17,002–25,000 TL, while 23.2% fell within the 25,001–35,000 TL range. Thus, most participants' incomes were slightly above the minimum wage based on 2024 figures. Most of the participants are single (52.9%). E-commerce site and social media usage statistics for the sample are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. E-commerce site and social media usage statistics for the sample

Attributes	E-Commere platforms	n	%
The most frequently used e-commerce company	Amazon	164	26.5
	Hepsiburada	190	30.6
	Trendyol	266	42.9
The most commonly used social media platform	Instagram	252	40.6
	YouTube	127	20.5
	Twitter	170	27.4
	Facebook	71	11.5
Daily time spent on social media	1-2 hours	208	33.6
	3-4 hours	322	51.9
	5-6 hours	57	9.2

	7-8 hours	33	5.3
Total		620	%100

Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis was performed on the scales. The Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated for the internal consistency of the scale, for each dimension and for the scale as a whole. The results obtained are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the scales

Scales	Number of statements before elimination	Pre-elimination cronbach's alpha	Number of statements after elimination	Post- elimination cronbach's alpha
Entertainment	2	0.797	2	0.797
Interaction	3	0.695	3	0.695
Trend-setting	2	0.648	2	0.648
Personalisation	2	0.783	2	0.783
Perceived Risk	2	0.460	-	-
Social Media Marketing	11	0.737	9	0.727
Word of Mouth Communication	5	0.590	4	0.620
Purchase Intention	5	0.731	5	0.731

Cronbach's alpha values exceeding 0.7 indicate high reliability (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018), though values above 0.6 are often Nunnally, 1978; Cortina, 1993; Hair et al., 2010 considered acceptable in certain contexts. This flexibility is particularly relevant when adapting scales across different samples or cultures (Hair et al., 2010:125). As shown in the results, the social media marketing and purchase intention scales demonstrated high reliability, while the word-of-mouth (WOM) scale showed acceptable reliability. Removing the first item of the WOM scale increased its alpha to 0.629; the initial value (0.590) was borderline, prompting examination of corrected item–total correlations. The first item (ewom1) showed a low correlation ($0.171 < 0.3$) with other items and was therefore excluded, resulting in acceptable reliability for the four-item scale.

Since Cronbach's alpha tends to rise with the number of items, dimensions with few items may yield lower coefficients due to limited shared variance. The

perceived risk dimension showed a particularly low alpha. Given that two-item scales are better evaluated with the Spearman–Brown coefficient (Eisinga, Grotenhuis & Pelzer, 2013:4), this statistic was computed (0.459), confirming inadequate reliability. Consequently, the perceived risk dimension was excluded from further analyses. The results of the KMO sample adequacy and Bartlett's sphericity test, which determine the adequacy of the data for factor analysis, are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. KMO ve Bartlett test results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sample Adequacy Test		.740
Bartlett's Sphericity Test	Approximately square	1837.729
	df (degree of freedom)	55
	p (significance)	.000

According to the table, the KMO value of 0.740 indicates that the sample is adequate for factor analysis. The significance of the Bartlett test of sphericity ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the matrix of relationships between variables of social media marketing is significant in terms of factor analysis and that factor analysis can be performed.

Table 5. Total variance explained results

Component	Eigenvalues			Post-Rotation Factor Loading Totals		
	Total	Variance (%)	Cumulative (%)	Total	Variance (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	3.256	29.599	29.599	1.923	17.481	17.481
2	1.964	17.851	47.450	1.736	15.780	33.261
3	1.202	10.932	58.382	1.705	15.495	48.756
4	1.024	9.313	67.694	1.504	13.677	62.433
5	.717	6.518	74.213	1.296	11.779	74.213
6	.655	5.951	80.164			
7	.598	5.433	85.597			
8	.513	4.663	90.260			
9	.426	3.872	94.132			
10	.328	2.986	97.118			
11	.317	2.882	100.000			

According to the table 5., a total of four factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were identified, and it was observed in the rotated component matrix that trendiness and personalization were grouped under the same factor. Therefore, although four factors emerged based on the sample/data, a five-factor limit was set to preserve the original scale structure and maintain the validity of the scale. The variables Entertainment, Interaction, Trendiness, Personalization, and Perceived Risk together explain approximately 74% of the variance in Social Media Marketing. Descriptive Statistics for each item in the scales are shown in table 6.

Table 6. Findings on descriptive statics

Dimensions	No	Item	N	\bar{X}	s
Entertainment	1	The social media site of the e-commerce company I use is entertaining	611	2.84	0.96
	2	The contents shared on the social media of the e-commerce company I use are entertaining.	611	2.87	1.02
Interaction	3	It is possible to share product/service information on the social media of the e-commerce company I use.	611	4.17	0.93
	4	It is possible to engage in discussions and exchange ideas on the social media of the e-commerce company I use.	611	4.36	0.81
	5	It is easy to express opinions on the social media of the e-commerce company I use.	611	4.27	0.87
Trendiness	6	The information shared on the social media of the e-commerce company I use is up to date.	611	3.50	1.01
	7	The social media use of the e-commerce company I use is consistent with current trends.	611	3.31	0.98
Personalization	8	I can find the information I need on the social media of the e-commerce company I use.	611	2.90	1.02

Electronic Word of Mouth	9	The social media of the e-commerce company I use provides the information I need.	611	2.84	0.95
	2	I send invitations to my friends to join a product/brand group on the social media site of the e-commerce company I use.	611	2.46	1.12
	3	When I see a product I like on the social media site of the e-commerce company I use, I use the “Like” or “+1” button to show my appreciation.	611	3.50	1.03
	4	I can say positive things about the products I like through social media.	611	4.16	0.77
	5	I send invitations to my friends to join brand or product groups that I believe they will like.	611	2.56	1.07
Purchase Intention	1	I would like to purchase the products and services of e-commerce businesses on social media.	611	3.59	0.93
	2	The presence of e-commerce businesses on social media may influence my preference for that business.	611	4.15	0.96
	3	When e-commerce businesses share appropriate (up-to-date, high-quality, etc.) content on social media, it may influence my preference for that business.	611	4.08	0.85
	4	I prefer to repurchase from e-commerce businesses with which I continue to interact through social media when I need something.	611	4.46	0.71
	5	When businesses respond via the same social media channel to my positive or negative comments about previous purchasing experiences, it may lead me to choose that business again.	611	4.72	0.63

As shown in Table 6, the purchase intention scale indicates that when brands respond to feedback shared on social media, the intention to repurchase is very high, with many participants strongly agreeing with this statement (4.72). Following these statements, the highest mean scores were observed within the interaction dimension of social media marketing, specifically for the items ‘Discussion and

exchange of ideas are possible on the social media of the e-commerce company I use’ and ‘It is easy to express opinions on the social media of the e-commerce company I use.’ Among the items with the lowest mean scores, the statement “I send invitations to my friends to join a product/brand group on the social media site of the e-commerce company I use” under the Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) dimension ranks first. In other words, participants tend to disagree with the idea of directly inviting friends via social media to join a product or brand group. These findings indicate that the attitude of ‘inviting’ is weak among users.

Findings Related to the First Hypothesis

The regression analysis conducted to test the first hypothesis revealed that social media marketing has a statistically significant effect on electronic word-of-mouth communication. The model demonstrated a moderate correlation ($R = 0.412$) and explained approximately 17% of the variance in electronic word-of-mouth ($R^2 = 0.170$). The adjusted R^2 value (0.169) further confirmed the robustness of the model. The F-statistic ($F = 124.732$, $p < 0.001$) indicated that the model was highly significant, supporting the hypothesis that social media marketing positively influences consumers’ tendency to engage in electronic word-of-mouth.

Table 7. Regression results on the effect of social media marketing dimensions on E-WOM

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error	F	p	Predictor(s)	Dependent Variable
1	0.412 ^a	0.170	0.169	0.626	124.732	0.000	Social Media Marketing	E-WOM
2	0.291 ^a	0.085	0.083	0.658	56.333	0.000	Entertainment	E-WOM
3	0.005 ^a	0.000	-0.002	0.688	0.015	0.902	Interaction	E-WOM
4	0.418 ^a	0.175	0.174	0.624	129.249	0.000	Trend Alignment	E-WOM
5	0.389 ^a	0.151	0.150	0.633	108.571	0.000	Personalization	E-WOM

The comparative results highlight that trend alignment and social media marketing have the most significant effects, while interaction shows no meaningful influence.

The evidence is notably consistent across recent research. Romadhoni et al., (2023) found that social media marketing and eWOM jointly explained 17.1% of variance in purchasing decisions. Tiffany michelle Jatmiko & Auditia Setiobudi, (2026) demonstrated a direct positive and significant effect of social media marketing on eWOM.

Findings Related to the Second Hypothesis

The second hypothesis of the research and the results of the sub-hypothesis tests belonging to this hypothesis are given below.

Table 8. Regression results in the effect of social media marketing dimensions on purchase intention

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error	F	p	Predictor(s)	Dependent Variable
1	0.235 ^a	0.055	0.054	0.518	35.664	0.000 ^b	Social Media Marketing	Purchase Intention
2	0.058 ^a	0.003	0.002	0.532	2.046	0.153 ^b	Entertainment	Purchase Intention
3	0.216 ^a	0.047	0.045	0.520	29.810	0.000 ^b	Interaction	Purchase Intention
4	0.237 ^a	0.056	0.054	0.518	36.083	0.000 ^b	Trend Alignment	Purchase Intention
5	0.088 ^a	0.008	0.006	0.531	4.745	0.030 ^b	Personalization	Purchase Intention

Results for second hypothesis present comparative regression model summaries. Models 1, 3, 4, and 5 demonstrate statistically significant predictive power ($p < .05$), with Model 4 showing the strongest explanatory capacity ($R^2 = .056$). Model 2 did not reach statistical significance ($p = .153$), indicating limited explanatory strength. Overall, the results suggest modest but meaningful variance explained across most models, with Model 4 emerging as the most robust.

This results also align well with the established literature (Cheung et al. 2021) showing that specific social media marketing elements have differential impacts, with interaction and trend alignment being more robust predictors than entertainment.

Findings Related to the Third Hypothesis

The third hypothesis of the research, “H3: Electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention,” was tested using linear regression analysis, and the model results are shown in the table 9

Table 9. Regression model results regarding the effect of electronic word-of-mouth communication on purchase intention

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error	F	p
1	0.279 ^a	0.078	0.076	0.512	51.501	0.000 ^b

According to the F-statistic the regression model is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Based on the R-value, there is a low-level positive correlation between electronic word-of-mouth communication and purchase intention. Consequently, it was determined that electronic word-of-mouth communication significantly influences purchase intention, and hypothesis H3 was supported.

Christy M. K. Cheung & D. Thadani, (2012) conducted a comprehensive literature analysis showing that eWOM communication has considerable impact on consumer behavior, providing an integrative framework explaining how eWOM influences consumer decision-making processes.

4. Discussions and Suggestions

This study examined the effects of social media marketing on consumers' e-WOM behavior and purchase intentions. The results indicate that social media marketing positively influences both e-WOM behaviors and purchase intentions. Specifically, among the elements of social media marketing, the dimensions of entertainment, trendiness, and personalization were found to positively affect e-WOM. However, the interaction factor was observed to have no significant effect on e-WOM. This suggests that the interaction consumers establish with brands on social media does not automatically translate into e-WOM behavior. On the other hand, while interaction, trendiness, and personalization were found to influence purchase intention, the entertainment dimension had no direct effect. Thus, although entertaining content is a successful element in engaging consumers, it does not directly impact purchasing decisions.

This is theoretically important because it suggests that hedonic content is more effective for generating sharing and online conversation, whereas utilitarian and relational cues are more important for converting attention into buying behavior. That logic fits prior studies showing that different SMM dimensions can activate different consumer responses. For example, Cheung et al. (2021) found that “Entertainment, customization and eWOM are the key predictors in driving consumers' value co-creation intention,” while “the impact of interactivity and trendiness on value co-creation intention is non-significant,” which is broadly consistent with your result that some social media features matter more than others. Bilal et al. (2021) stated that “interaction, entertainment, eWOM, and trendiness are core factors” for consumer purchase-related outcomes, although in this study differs by showing that entertainment drives e-WOM but not purchase intention.

Also results are also aligned with studies that found stronger effects for personalization and interaction than for broad “social media marketing” effects. Ho et al. (2024) found a more refined structure in the property sector, where entertainment, interaction, customization, and word-of-mouth were positive, but trendiness was only weakly positive and insignificant for purchase intention. By contrast, Chuah et al. (2023) reported that all five SMM dimensions significantly

affected purchase intention in cosmetics, showing that the strength and direction of SMM effects vary by product category, platform use, and consumer context.

Theoretically, this study expands on social media marketing research by demonstrating that word-of-mouth communication (e-WOM) and purchase intention do not stem from the same antecedents. Thus, it suggests to the literature that e-WOM functions as a distinct mediator and consumer response, rather than simply another form of purchase intention. In other words, managers should not assume that entertaining content alone will convert into sales. Entertainment appears useful for creating conversation and shareability, but purchase intention depends more on content that feels personally relevant, timely, and interaction-friendly. The indirect effects of entertaining content on consumer behavior should be investigated by examining variables such as brand awareness and attitude to determine which mechanisms are more effective in the transition to purchasing behavior. For this reason, the results may support a differentiated strategy—for instance, using entertainment to initiate engagement and e-WOM, and then reinforcing that engagement with personalized and interactive content that reduces purchase uncertainty and enhances perceived relevance.

The study still has some limits. First of all it uses a questionnaire-based, cross-sectional design, so the relationships are associative rather than causal, and all variables come from the same survey source, which raises the possibility of common-method bias. Secondly the sample is also context-specific, so the pattern may reflect the platform and consumer environment according to data rather than a universal SMM effect. Those limits matter because several comparison studies in the literature also show context-sensitive results, especially for trendiness and interaction, which means the model may not transfer unchanged across product types or markets.

These limitations suggest clear next steps. Future research should test the model in other sectors and countries, use probability sampling where possible, and compare different social media platforms rather than treating them as equivalent. A longitudinal design would help separate immediate e-WOM reactions from later purchase behavior, and mediation models could test whether brand awareness, attitude, trust, brand equity, or customer engagement explain why some SMM dimensions convert into purchase intention while others mainly drive sharing. It would also be useful to test whether e-WOM acts as a mediator between entertainment and purchase intention, because this study imply that entertaining content may influence buying indirectly rather than directly. This is an initial results from a quick literature review, so a deeper literature analysis can sharpen the results further.

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